

Smart_TEM – New techniques for end-to-end digitization of telecom invoice processing

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Data availability statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available on request from the corresponding author. The data are not publicly available due to privacy restrictions.

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ABSTRACT

Telecommunications Expense Management (TEM) is one of the most significant operating-cost items for companies in banking, insurance, health care, and contact-center sectors. The Smart_TEM project develops an innovative solution to fully automate TEM in enterprises, focusing especially on invoice scrutiny and processing. Traditional manual invoice review is time- and resource-intensive and prone to errors and inconsistencies. This project addresses the problem through advanced artificial-intelligence (AI) techniques, including machine learning, deep neural networks, and natural-language processing (NLP).

The methodology comprises automated digital capture of invoices via OCR, automatic classification and labelling of extracted data, and their detailed analysis to pinpoint discrepancies between billed and contracted items, including undue charges or cost overruns. The system automatically compares the invoice information with a knowledge base generated from contracts and other related documents.

Smart_TEM also performs automatic detection of more advantageous tariff alternatives through web-scraping techniques and customised comparators. Built on a microservices architecture, the platform offers efficient scalability and secure data handling.

The project successfully reached Technology Readiness Level 7 (TRL 7), demonstrating its functionality in a real operational environment in partnership with a Spanish call-center company. Tests showed significant improvements in accuracy and efficiency over traditional methods, thanks to custom OCR and machine-learning models trained on real data. The system also proved capable of adapting to diverse invoice formats and of continuously improving through supervised feedback.

The project is now moving toward TRL 9 for commercial deployment, with a technology roadmap that includes enhancements such as advanced predictive analytics, integrated business rules, multi-client interfaces, and additional features to further optimise automated expense management.

I. INTRODUCTION

Corporate spending on telecommunications services is one of the most significant operating-cost elements for companies in banking, insurance, health care, contact centers, retail, and other sectors. In such firms, managing telecommunications expenses (TEM) is complex, largely because of the wide range of services offered by telecom operators and the specific intricacies of each company.

Invoice review is a key TEM activity, as a substantial share of billed amounts often corresponds to improper charges [1]: mislabelled items, uncontracted services, oversized units, wrong tariffs, etc.

The global telecommunications market amounts to USD 1.9 trillion. Roughly 80 % of invoices for these services contain errors, and where errors exist, the deviations average about 8 % of the total billed amount [2]. Yet manually verifying invoice contents against contracted terms is costly, slow, and yields inconsistent results.

Invoice review and approval processes aim to ensure that a document is correct—that its contents match contractual terms, milestones, items, and expected costs. Only after an invoice has been reviewed and approved is it forwarded to accounting for payment processing.

Companies typically perform a two-tier review: an initial functional review followed by a detailed review.

- **Functional review.** Once an invoice is received and recorded, the manager of the cost-owning department performs a superficial “sanity check” to ensure that the content and cost are coherent with the contracted product or service. This is only a

preliminary, simple verification aimed at discarding obviously erroneous invoices without incurring the cost of an exhaustive review.

- Detailed review. After the functional check, the contract manager—or a delegate—verifies that the billed items are admissible and included in the contract, that quantities or units are correct, and that costs align with agreed tariffs.

Reviewing invoices requires full knowledge of invoice formats, item codifications, contract terms, and the infrastructure covered by the service.

When a non-conformity is detected, the usual channel is a claim through customer service or the relevant department of the service provider. Once the claim is filed, the issuer opens a case that may take several days to resolve. If accepted, the process ends with an amended invoice.

The generic review process described does not encompass other elements that should be checked periodically, such as the applicability of better tariffs or the existence of alternative products or services better suited to contracted purposes.

The overall objective of Smart_TEM is to develop a new solution for managing telecommunications expenses by end-to-end automating the process's most critical component: invoice-item review. This process includes data acquisition, classification, and analysis to identify oversized costs, undue charges, and more advantageous tariff alternatives that can yield net expense reductions.

The solution relies on multiple AI techniques, including machine learning, neural networks, and NLP.

The project sought to reach TRL 7. Accordingly, it included building a full prototype with new intelligence layers and demonstrating and validating it in a real-world pilot.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Automating invoice processing and information extraction attracts considerable academic and business interest. Invoice digitisation is a mature field dating back to the 1990s yet still evolving because of heterogeneous formats and the image degradation typical of scans [3]. Nearly all developments follow a four-step pipeline: preprocessing; text-and-table detection; optical-character recognition (OCR); and information extraction [4].

The technical challenge is complex: invoices are among the financial documents with the greatest structural and format heterogeneity. When an invoice's main structure is known in advance, parsing is easier, so most studies focus on classifying known invoice types or extracting information from them [5].

Other authors employ Support Vector Machine (SVM) classifiers to discover previously unknown invoice classes [6]. Each invoice is assigned either to an existing class or to a newly created one. Document-level image features match a given invoice against known types while ignoring minor differences, such as stamps and signatures.

Rule-based invoice-processing systems classify documents using either issuer-specific or generic extraction rules [7]. For unknown document types, some systems apply case-based reasoning (CBR) to approximate the most similar document class [8].

Most invoice-processing systems assume document classes exist; thus, deciding the document class label is critical, and any mistake invalidates downstream analysis. Some works propose eliminating classes altogether and modelling invoice parsing as a generic object-detection problem [9], locating sender details, dates, line items, tax-ID numbers, etc.

Automating item review involves comparing invoice item descriptions against information in purchase orders, contracts, quotes, or other documents. As descriptions are often not well-formed sentences, semantic- or syntactic-similarity approaches may not apply. Some authors advocate supervised-learning techniques such as similarity-classification algorithms [10].

Certain studies highlight the need for document-ontology alignment tools or ontology-negotiation protocols to ensure the system can handle upload/download phases [8]. Other works transform invoice information into semantic models, e.g., OWL ontologies, which is complex, particularly when mapping XML-based electronic invoices to OWL [11].

In analysing extracted data, a main technical goal is detecting deviations and outliers. Outlier detection aims to find objects in a dataset that deviate from expected patterns. Typical algorithms take a collection of objects described by feature vectors. Some authors have developed detectors for objects described by multiple feature vectors (object-matrix) [12].

Combining multiple machine-learning outlier-detection methods yields good results; literature shows that ensembles outperform single methods [13]. Such systems build an algorithm selecting the final output by balancing each method's result, and selection-algorithm design critically affects model stability and accuracy.

The project's final line of work concerns identifying better tariff alternatives. Price-comparison tools have long operated on e-commerce data, periodically updating information and matching identical products with slightly different descriptions or languages [14]. These shopping bots combine semantic web, NLP, multi-agent systems, and web-data-mining technologies [15]. More advanced comparison systems rely on genetic algorithms to construct automated valuation models under uncertainty [16].

III. METHODOLOGY

Invoice matching is a key activity for Accounts Payable departments, yet complex and resource-intensive. Smart_TEM aims to create a digital solution that, through an automated process governed by various AI techniques, drastically reduces these costs in telecommunications-expense management.

The system acts as a hub for cost information related to a client's technology, clarifying and organising both communication processes with suppliers (e.g., invoices, quotes, contracts, commitments) and the data itself.

Once stored, data-analysis and exception-detection processes identify deviations for subsequent management, escalation, and claims. This enables automated audits and consultancy on contracted processes and products.

Invoice matching compares invoice information with associated documents such as contracts, payment schedules, purchase orders, or inventory records. Its goals are accurate supplier payments, correct cost accounting, contract compliance, and quick detection of potentially fraudulent invoices.

A invoice deviation (exception) occurs when invoice details do not match supporting documents. The three most common deviations are:

- Item mismatch: a billed product or service is not contracted.
- Quantity mismatch: billed units differ from those in the contract or order.
- Price mismatch: the unit price on the invoice differs from the contract or PO price.

When a deviation is identified, the root cause is determined, acceptability assessed, and, if necessary, corrective action is coordinated with the supplier.

The project aims for touchless invoice processing: fully autonomous matching. Once the system confirms that all invoice data align with supporting documents and tolerance levels, the invoice can proceed from receipt and data capture to final posting in the ERP for payment—without human intervention.

The system autonomously detects:

- Items that do not align with supporting documentation.
- Costs that deviate from historical metrics beyond predefined tolerances.

Thanks to AI, the system understands invoice content, identifying items that might be optimised—either because better offers exist for the same product/service or because more appropriate technologies are available.

IIIA. FUNCTIONAL DESCRIPTION

The proposed system operates as follows:

1. Document collection. Inputs (invoices) are automatically ingested in digital format through a dedicated portal or API. Invoices received as scanned images via channels such as email are processed through image analysis and OCR.
2. Document examination. The file is classified before data extraction and labelling. Classification, data extraction, and labelling are fully robotic processes executed by trained models.
3. Data analysis targets four elements:
 - a. Price deviations from expected values.
 - b. Discrepancies between billed and contracted units.
 - c. Presence of uncontracted items.
 - d. Use of tariffs or technologies that could be improved.

To perform this autonomously, the AI is trained to understand concepts—complicated by each supplier’s unique nomenclature. It also learns to detect cost deviations and raise alerts.

4. Reference sources. The analysis draws on contracts and supplier product catalogues. New catalogue products are processed automatically—registered, classified, and parameterised without manual coding.
5. Tariff and technology assessment. The intelligence layer evaluates whether optimal tariffs and the most suitable technologies are in use.
6. Alert handling. Alerts follow two separate workflows:
 - a. Deviations are managed like ticketing incidents, opening a non-conformity with the supplier and requesting invoice correction.
 - b. Tariff/technology change proposals may involve more complex management; technological changes affecting physical infrastructure may trigger formal projects with implementation and maintenance phases.
7. Outcome recording. All data on resolved deviations, incidents, and proposals are properly logged. Recovered undue charges and generated savings feed into billing to each client.

Illustration 1. Basic functional diagram of the solution.

IIIB. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

Smart_TEM is built on a microservices architecture, supporting modular scalability in functionality and performance and enabling service containerisation in frameworks such as Docker, Amazon ECS, Azure ACS, or Kubernetes.

Illustration 2. General system architecture.

Key architectural elements:

- Document intake. Depending on client needs and infrastructure, intake uses:
 - a. Manual collection: portal upload, scanning, bulk upload.
 - b. Automatic collection from supplier portals: RPA, web services, API.
 - c. Email reception.

Raw information is stored in an unclassified project repository. Adding a new file triggers a collection process that routes it to extraction.

- Processing and extraction. First, documents are discriminated by class (invoice or contract) to generate asynchronous events:
 - a. Contracts and annexes are processed to identify items, prices, commitments, volume discounts, or service SLAs.

- b. For invoices, the module processes visual information and file metadata to produce raw document data for the Classification module.

Extractions feed a database as raw data, using recognition techniques such as Multi-Class SVM and supplying the AI, which classifies based on prior training or supervised retraining.

- Classification. Machine-learning and NLP algorithms plus business rules classify data. Unclassified data are approximated to existing classes via clustering. Supervised retraining based on client feedback incorporates new or unknown items and acceptable cost overruns, adapting business rules.
- Data analysis includes three features:
 - a. Undue Products. Control of recurring products and alerting on additional items based on contract concepts and historical usage.
 - b. Costs Overrun. Alerts on undue costs within established items, according to contract agreements.
 - c. Comparator. Queries supplier data and proposes improvements within the client's contractual products, considering commitments and penalties. Comparisons are not line-by-line but can propose cheaper products with the same functionality (e.g., replacing a pay-as-you-go link without QoS by MPLS, or switching capped corporate data plans to unlimited).

These features rely on various algorithms and may trigger asynchronous processes such as alerts or queries to suppliers or clients.

- Data presentation. Smart_TEM allows queries on all data—extracted invoice data or resulting analytics—via a real-time dashboard, scheduled email reports, or instant extractions.
- Security. Two entry vectors are envisaged:
 - a. File input via connection:
 - i. Non-standard ports.
 - ii. Point-to-point firewall filtering by IP.
 - iii. Preferably on-premise bastioned RPA.
 - b. Frontend queries for management and consultation.

An edge firewall with deny-all and restrictive origin-IP policies guards these vectors.

IV. RESULTS

Through diverse AI techniques and process automation, the project fully achieved its overarching goal, developing several proofs of concept and a functional prototype.

During development, advanced Machine-Learning and Deep-Learning techniques improved data extraction and analysis:

- Machine-Learning models (supervised) classified and analysed data, identifying patterns and anomalies in invoices. Trained on historical data, they improved accuracy and generalisation.
- Deep-Learning models enhanced textual-data extraction and association of product and sub-product structures, refined through iterative tuning to handle diverse invoice formats.
- Natural-Language Processing interpreted textual invoice data, enabling the system to manage various formats and languages, understand context and semantics, and improve comparison and validation accuracy.

OCR was crucial for extracting data from scanned invoices. Initial tests with Azure OCR offered quick deployment but did not generalise well to Martel's specific invoice formats. Custom OCR solutions were therefore developed, improving data-extraction accuracy across broader invoice formats and key data (product, quantity, price).

Custom business rules enhanced extraction accuracy and ensured consistent, reliable data. These rules enabled better handling of exceptions and special cases, improving overall precision.

The project scope targeted TRL 7, successfully achieved, as the prototype was demonstrated and validated in a real-world pilot.

IVA. INVOICE PROCESSING AND DATA EXTRACTION

Software for invoice processing and data extraction was one of the project's most critical, challenging areas. A three-phase approach addressed this:

1. Initial implementation with Azure. Microsoft Azure ML services were evaluated but did not generalise well to Martel's invoice types, prompting exploration of other solutions.

2. Use of OCR. OCR techniques ensured accurate text reading. Though not always generalisable, they provided initial extraction for developing more advanced solutions.
3. Custom Deep-Learning models. Specific DL models for invoice reading and understanding achieved good text-extraction results but struggled to associate product/sub-product structures.

Ultimately, OCR combined with specific rules ensured precise extraction of key data (product, quantity, price) from suppliers such as Vodafone and Ono. This hybrid approach offered flexibility and accuracy across varied invoice formats.

Illustration 3. Invoice processing in Smart_TEM (frontend + backend view).

IVB. DETECTION OF COST OVERRUNS AND UNDUE ITEMS

Identifying cost overruns and undue items relied on a comparison script (“merge”) between current invoices and a knowledge base (contracts). The script compares an invoice data file with a contract data file, detecting cost and quantity deviations and allowing users to validate and persist data, continuously improving system accuracy.

The process of detecting cost overruns and undue items was carried out as follows:

- Comparison of invoices and contracts. The ‘merge’ script compares the data extracted from the invoices with the contract data stored in the knowledge base.

- Deviation detection. Deviations in costs and quantities between invoices and contracts are identified, flagging any discrepancies as a possible cost overrun or misconception.
- Validation and persistence. Users can validate and persist corrections in the knowledge base, ensuring that future comparisons are more accurate and reliable.

In detail, the comparison process encoded in Smart_TEM is as follows:

1. Initial data extraction. Using OCR and Machine Learning techniques, all data is extracted from invoices and contracts. This data includes information on products, quantities and prices.
2. Knowledge base creation. An initial knowledge base is built using data from existing contracts. This knowledge base is used as a reference for the comparison of future invoices.
3. Execution of the comparison script. The merge script compares the invoice data with the data in the knowledge base. Discrepancies in costs and quantities are identified and flagged for review.
4. Validation and update. Users validate detected discrepancies and update the knowledge base as necessary. This validation may include acceptance of new rates or correction of erroneous data in the knowledge base.
5. Data persistence. Validated data is persisted in the knowledge base to improve the accuracy of future comparisons. This learning process ensures that the system becomes more accurate and reliable over time.

Illustration 4. Validation and persistence process in Smart_TEM (frontend + backend view).

IVC. AUTOMATED SEARCH FOR TARIFF ALTERNATIVES

Web-scraping techniques automated the search for better tariffs on supplier websites. Scripts extracted tariff information from providers such as Vodafone and MásMóvil, running periodically to keep tariff data current.

Because online offers did not always match contract-specific products, two alternatives were considered for demonstration:

- Custom REST API. Simulate supplier responses, enabling precise comparisons even when no exact online-offer match exists.
- Landing-page offers. Create a page with offers resembling contract-specific products, enabling an effective demonstration.

IVD. TESTING AND VALIDATION

Testing was continuous, using real invoices from Marktél and other suppliers. These tests included:

- Data-extraction comparison. Extracted invoice data were compared with contracts to identify and correct discrepancies.
- Deviation-validation. Detected deviations were validated and knowledge-base adjustments made to improve accuracy.

- Web-scraping trials. Offer-extraction accuracy was evaluated and techniques fine-tuned.
- Automation tests. Scripts were tested to ensure efficient handling of large data volumes and comparisons.

V. CONCLUSIONS

The main objective of the Smart_TEM project has been to develop a software solution that automates the review of the concepts and amounts present in telecommunications invoices, in search of undue charges or deviations with respect to what was contracted.

The review of invoices is a very important process in the financial administration of companies. This process is traditionally carried out manually, being resource intensive (staff hours) and obtaining inconsistent results over time. The use case developed in Smart_TEM was telecommunications expenses, due to the enormous margin for improvement that an automated review of invoices in this type of services can offer.

Within the process to be automated in Smart_TEM, AI algorithms have been developed for the extraction of bill data, its classification and analysis for the detection of oversized costs or undue charges. A proof of concept has also been made for the extraction of tariff information through web scraping.

The scope of the project was to exceed a technology maturity level of TRL7, which required a pilot test in a real operating environment. To this end, a partnership agreement was signed during the application phase with MARKTEL, a Spanish contact centre company with a significant monthly spend on telephony, internet and other telecommunication services. This collaboration has been positively implemented.

To achieve the overall objective described above, the project was structured in four phases. First, the scope of the pilot was defined, which involved the analysis of the technological infrastructure and systems of the partner company. Subsequently, two phases were executed in parallel: the development of the prototype and the implementation of the AI models. The development of the prototype software was carried out using an agile methodology, which allowed for continuous iteration and improvement of the code during the process.

In the AI implementation phase of the system, machine learning and deep learning models were integrated, as well as text recognition and natural language processing techniques for data extraction and classification. These models were trained on real available data and documents, improving their ability to identify patterns and anomalies in invoices.

In the development of AI models, we collaborated with a research group from the University of La Laguna (ULL, Spain), which provided scientific and technical advice in the field of artificial intelligence and language technologies.

Finally, the pilot was executed, where the prototype was tested in a real operating environment. This phase included training of staff, monitoring of the system and development of corrective actions to remedy problems with the tool.

The project has been successfully completed, achieving all the objectives initially set, and work is already underway to achieve a TRL9 technology maturity level that will allow the product to be commercialised. Moreover, the success in the development of this project allows us to be ambitious for the future. A technological roadmap has already been established for the evolution of Smart_TEM in the medium and long term, which includes the implementation of new functionalities such as the integration of business rules, multi-language frontend, multi-client application, or advanced predictive analytics functionalities, among others.

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